

Advancements in Fixed Point Theory for Fuzzy Normed Spaces Using the Common Limit Range Method with Application

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ABSTRACT:

This paper explores novel fixed point theorems for weakly compatible mappings in fuzzy normed spaces (fns) that adhere to an implicit relation. By employing the concepts of the common limit range property (CLR) and the common property ($E.A$), we establish new results in this field. Several illustrative examples are provided to validate the hypotheses and highlight the applicability of our findings. Furthermore, as an applied approach of our primary results, we establish a common fixed point theorem of integral type within fuzzy normed space.

Keywords: Fuzzy normed space, The common limit range property (CLR), The common property ($E.A$), Theorem of common fixed points of integral type.

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INTRODUCTION

Since its introduction by [1], the concept of fuzzy set has served as a cornerstone for numerous extensions in mathematical analysis, particularly in normed spaces. [2] introduced the framework of fuzzy normed spaces in 1984, which has since been extensively studied [3-8]. The development of fuzzy normed spaces has facilitated the expansion of classical fixed point theory, a crucial area in nonlinear analysis with wide-ranging applications. Fixed point theory and functional analysis have found increasing applications across diverse fields, including economics, physics, astronomy, and game theory.

[9] established theorems of common fixed point for mappings in fns utilizing the notion of compatibility. Mazaheri, Dehghan, and [10] introduced the concept of approximate-fixed points in fns and provided theorems of existence. [11] formulated and demonstrated contraction mappings's fixed point theorems in fns . Additionally, Several other researchers have investigated fixed point theorems in fuzzy normed spaces, contributing to the advancement of this mathematical domain.

In this study, we derive new common fixed point theorems for weakly compatible mappings satisfying the common limit range property (CLR) and the property ($E.A$) within fns . Furthermore, we present supplementary results along with illustrative examples to substantiate our findings. As a practical

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extension of our primary results, we introduce an integral-type common fixed point theorem in fuzzy normed spaces.

PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1. [12]: If \mathcal{U} is a linear space, $*$ is a continuous t-norm, and \mathfrak{F} is a fuzzy set on $\mathcal{U} \times (0, \infty)$ to $[0, 1]$, then a tuple $(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{F}, *)$ is considered a fuzzy normed space (*fns*) if it satisfies the following requirements: for any $a, b \in \mathcal{U}, s, t > 0$,

1. $\mathfrak{F}(a, s) > 0$,
2. $\mathfrak{F}(a, s) = 1 \leftrightarrow a = 0$,
3. $\mathfrak{F}(\sigma a, s) = \mathfrak{F}\left(a, \frac{s}{|\sigma|}\right) \forall \sigma \in R/\{0\}$,
4. $\mathfrak{F}(a, s) * \mathfrak{F}(b, t) \leq \mathfrak{F}(a + b, s + t)$,
5. $\mathfrak{F}(a, \cdot): (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous,
6. $\lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{F}(a, s) = 1$.

Example 2.1. [12]: Consider the normed space $(\mathcal{U}, \|\cdot\|)$. For every $x, y \in [0, 1]$, write $as x * y = xy$ (or $x * y = \min\{x, y\}$). Moreover, let $\mathfrak{F}_{\|\cdot\|}$ be fuzzy sets on $\mathcal{U} \times (0, \infty)$, which are defined as follow: $\mathfrak{F}_{\|\cdot\|}(a, s) = \frac{s}{s + \|a\|}$. The fuzzy normed space \mathfrak{F} caused by the norm $\|\cdot\|$ is commonly known as the standard fuzzy norm, and $(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{F}_{\|\cdot\|}, *)$ is a *fns*.

Lemma 2.1. [13]: Consider the *fns* $(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{F}, *)$, For any $a \in \mathcal{U}$, $\mathfrak{F}(a, s)$ is non-decreasing.

Definition 2.2. [14]: When $\{a_n\}$ is a sequence in \mathcal{U} such that $\mathcal{S}_{a_n} \rightarrow w$ for some $w \in \mathcal{U}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then the pair $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ of a *fns*'s self-mappings of $(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{F}, *)$ is considered compatible if $\mathfrak{F}(\mathcal{A}\mathcal{S}_{a_n} - \mathcal{S}\mathcal{A}_{a_n}, t) \rightarrow 1$, for all $s > 0$.

Definition 2.3. [15]: A pair $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ of self-mappings on a non-empty set \mathcal{U} is called weakly compatible if there exists some $w \in \mathcal{U}$ such that $\mathcal{A}w = \mathcal{S}w$, then it must also hold that $\mathcal{A}\mathcal{S}w = \mathcal{S}\mathcal{A}w$.

Definition 2.4. [16]: (Implicit function)

Let \mathcal{Q}_6 represent a collection of all continuous functions $\mathcal{Q}, \mathcal{Q}: [0, 1]^6 \rightarrow R$ meeting the requirements:

1. \mathcal{Q} in $\sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, \sigma_5$ and σ_6 is decreasing.
2. For any $u, v \in [0, 1]$, $u \geq v$ is implied by $\mathcal{Q}(u, v, v, v, v, v) \geq 0$.

Example 2.2. [16]: The following functions are implicit,

1. $\mathcal{Q}(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, \sigma_5, \sigma_6) = \sigma_1 - \min\{\sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, \sigma_5, \sigma_6\}$.
2. $\mathcal{Q}(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, \sigma_5, \sigma_6) = \sigma_1^2 - \min\{\sigma_i \sigma_j: i, j \in \{2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}\}$.
3. $\mathcal{Q}(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, \sigma_5, \sigma_6) = \sigma_1^3 - \min\{\sigma_i \sigma_j \sigma_k: i, j, k \in \{2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}\}$.

MAIN RESULTS

Definition 3.1: The property (*E. A.*) is satisfied by a pair $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ of self mappings of *fns* $(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{F}, *)$ if there is a sequence $\{a_n\}$ in \mathcal{U} such that, for some $w \in \mathcal{U}$ $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{A}a_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{S}a_n = w$.

Remark 3.1: According to Definition 2.2, a self mappings \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{S} of a *fns* $(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{F}, *)$ is considered non-compatible if there is at least one sequence $\{a_n\}$ in \mathcal{U} so that $w \in \mathcal{U}$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{A}a_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{S}a_n = w$, but for some $s > 0$, $\mathfrak{F}(\mathcal{A}\mathcal{S}_{a_n} - \mathcal{S}\mathcal{A}_{a_n}, s)$ is less than 1 or non-existent. Accordingly, a pair of incompatible mappings of a *fns* $(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{F}, *)$ satisfy the condition (*E. A.*) in light of Definition 3.1, but the opposite need not be true.

Definition 3.2: If there are two sequences $\{a_n\}, \{b_n\}$ in \mathcal{U} then two pairings $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{T})$ of self mappings of a $fns(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{H}, *)$ are considered to fulfill the common (E.A.) property if for some $w \in \mathcal{U}$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{A}a_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{S}a_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{B}b_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{T}b_n = w$.

Definition 3.3: If there exists a sequence $\{a_n\}$ in \mathcal{U} such that, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{A}a_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{S}a_n = w \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U})$, then a pair of self-mappings $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ in a $fns(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{H}, *)$ is said to fulfill the common limit range property concerning the mapping \mathcal{S} , also referred to as the $(CLR_{\mathcal{S}})$ condition.

Definition 3.4: Given two sequences $\{a_n\}$ and $\{b_n\}$ in \mathcal{U} , if they satisfy the condition $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{A}a_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{S}a_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{B}b_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{T}b_n = w$, where w belongs to the intersection $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U}) \cap \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$, then the pairs of self-mappings $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{T})$ in a $fns(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{H}, *)$ are said to satisfy the common limit range property with respect to both mappings \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{T} , denoted as the $(CLR_{\mathcal{S}\mathcal{T}})$ condition.

Definition 3.5: If the following conditions are held:

1. $\mathcal{A}_i \mathcal{A}_j = \mathcal{A}_j \mathcal{A}_i, \forall i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$,
2. $\mathcal{S}_k \mathcal{S}_l = \mathcal{S}_l \mathcal{S}_k, \forall k, l \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$,
3. $\mathcal{A}_i \mathcal{S}_k = \mathcal{S}_k \mathcal{A}_i, \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ and $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

Then the two collections of self-mappings $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i=1}^m$ and $\{\mathcal{S}_k\}_{k=1}^n$ are defined as pairwise commuting.

Lemma 3.1: Let $(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{H}, *)$ be a fns such that for every $\sigma \in [0, 1], \sigma * \sigma \geq \sigma$. Let $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{B}$ and \mathcal{T} be mapping from \mathcal{U} to itself that meet the following criteria:

1. The $CLR_{\mathcal{S}}$ (or $CLR_{\mathcal{T}}$) property is satisfied by the pair $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ (or $(\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{T})$),
2. $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{U}) \subset \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$ (or $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{U}) \subset \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U})$),
3. \mathcal{U} has a closed subset $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U})$ or $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$.
4. Every sequence $\{b_n\}$ in \mathcal{U} is convergent under \mathcal{B} whenever it is convergent under \mathcal{T} (or any sequence $\{a_n\}$ in \mathcal{U} is convergent under \mathcal{A} whenever it is convergent under \mathcal{S})
5. There exists a constant $p \in (0, 1)$ such that

$$\Omega(\mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}a - \mathcal{B}b, p\sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{S}a - \mathcal{T}b, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}a - \mathcal{S}a, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{B}b - \mathcal{T}b, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}a - \mathcal{T}b, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{B}b - \mathcal{S}a, \sigma)) \geq 0, \text{ for all } a, b \in \mathcal{U}, \sigma > 0 \text{ and } \Omega \in \Omega_6. \quad (1)$$

Then, the $(CLR_{\mathcal{S}\mathcal{T}})$ attribute is shared by the pairings $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{T})$.

Proof: There is a sequence $\{a_n\}$ in \mathcal{U} such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{A}a_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{S}a_n = w$, where $w \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U})$, since the pair $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ satisfies the $(CLR_{\mathcal{S}})$ condition. For every sequence $\{a_n\}$ in \mathcal{U} , there exists a sequence $\{b_n\}$ such that $\mathcal{A}a_n = \mathcal{T}b_n$, and by (2), $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{U}) \subset \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$. Consequently, because $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$ is closed, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{T}b_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{A}a_n = w$, in this case, $w \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U}) \cap \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$. As $n \rightarrow \infty$, we thus get $\mathcal{A}a_n \rightarrow w, \mathcal{S}a_n \rightarrow w$ and $\mathcal{T}b_n \rightarrow w$. The sequence $\mathcal{B}(b_n)$ converges by (4), and we must demonstrate that $\mathcal{B}b_n \rightarrow w$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Conversely, suppose that $\mathcal{B}b_n \rightarrow w' (\neq w)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. We obtain

$$\Omega(\mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}a - \mathcal{B}b, p\sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{S}a - \mathcal{T}b, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}a - \mathcal{S}a, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{B}b - \mathcal{T}b, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}a - \mathcal{T}b, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{B}b - \mathcal{S}a, \sigma)) \geq 0$$

When employing inequality (1) with $a = a_n, b = b_n$.

Assuming that $n \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\text{we obtain } \Omega(\mathfrak{H}(w - w', p\sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w' - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w' - w, \sigma)) \geq 0$$

Or equivalently,

$$\Omega(\mathfrak{H}(w - w', p\sigma), 1, 1, \mathfrak{H}(w' - w, \sigma), 1, \mathfrak{H}(w' - w, \sigma)) \geq 0$$

Since Ω is decreasing in $\sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, \sigma_5, \sigma_6$ we get $\Omega(\mathfrak{H}(w - w', p\sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w - w', \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w - w', \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w' - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w' - w, \sigma)) \geq 0$

We obtain $\mathfrak{H}(w' - w, p\sigma) \geq \mathfrak{H}(w' - w, \sigma)$ from Ω_2 . we arrive at $w = w'$.

Consequently, the pairings $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{T})$ satisfy the $(CLR_{\mathcal{ST}})$ property since $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{b_n} = w$.

Theorem 3.1: Let $(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{H}, *)$ be a *fns* such that for every $\sigma \in [0, 1], \sigma * \sigma \geq \sigma$. Let \mathcal{U} be mapped into itself by $\mathcal{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathcal{S}$ and \mathcal{T} in order to meet inequality (1). Assume that the $(CLR_{\mathcal{ST}})$ property is enjoyed by the pairing $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{T})$ following that, each of the pairs $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{T})$ has a coincidence point. Furthermore, as long as the pairs $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{T})$ and $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ are weakly compatible, $\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{T}, \mathcal{A}$ and \mathcal{S} share a single fixed point.

Proof:

There are two sequences $\{a_n\}$ and $\{b_n\}$ in \mathcal{U} such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{A}a_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{S}a_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{b_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{T}b_n = w$, given that the pairings $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{T})$ and $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ fulfill the $(CLR_{\mathcal{ST}})$ property. In this case, $w \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U}) \cap \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$. There is a point $u \in \mathcal{U}$ such that $\mathcal{S}_u = w$ since $w \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U})$. Initially, we prove that $\mathcal{S}_u = \mathcal{A}_u$, by placing $a = u$ and $b = b_n$ in (1), then

$$\Omega(\mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_u - \mathfrak{B}_{b_n}, p\sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{S}_u - \mathcal{T}_{b_n}, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_u - \mathcal{S}_u, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathfrak{B}_{b_n} - \mathcal{T}_{b_n}, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_u - \mathcal{T}_{b_n}, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathfrak{B}_{b_n} - \mathcal{S}_u, \sigma)) \geq 0$$

which on making $n \rightarrow \infty$, reduces to

$$\Omega(\mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_u - w, p\sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_u - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_u - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w - w, \sigma)) \geq 0 \text{ and so,}$$

$$\Omega(\mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_u - w, p\sigma), 1, \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_u - w, \sigma), 1, \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_u - w, \sigma), 1) \geq 0$$

We obtain $\mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_u - w, p\sigma) \geq \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_u - w, \sigma)$ from Ω_1 and Ω_2 . Since $\mathcal{A}_u = w$, thus $\mathcal{A}_u = \mathcal{S}_u = w$, indicating that u is a point of coincidence for the pair $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$. Additionally, given that $w \in \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$, there is a point $v \in \mathcal{U}$ where $\mathcal{T}_v = w$. We now claim that $\mathfrak{B}_v = \mathcal{T}_v$. On using (1) with $a = u, b = v$ we have

$$\Omega(\mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_u - \mathfrak{B}_v, p\sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{S}_u - \mathcal{T}_v, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_u - \mathcal{S}_u, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathfrak{B}_v - \mathcal{T}_v, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_u - \mathcal{T}_v, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathfrak{B}_v - \mathcal{S}_u, \sigma)) \geq 0$$

which reduced to

$$\Omega(\mathfrak{H}(w - \mathfrak{B}_v, p\sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathfrak{B}_v - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathfrak{B}_v - w, \sigma)) \geq 0$$

or, equivalently,

$$\Omega(\mathfrak{H}(w - \mathfrak{B}_v, p\sigma), 1, 1, \mathfrak{H}(\mathfrak{B}_v - w, \sigma), 1, \mathfrak{H}(\mathfrak{B}_v - w, \sigma)) \geq 0$$

We obtain $\mathfrak{H}(w - \mathfrak{B}_v, p\sigma) \geq \mathfrak{H}(w - \mathfrak{B}_v, \sigma)$ from Ω_1 and Ω_2 . we obtain $w = \mathfrak{B}_v$. This indicates that v is a point of coincidence for the pair $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{T}), \mathfrak{B}_v = \mathcal{T}_v = w$

Given that $\mathcal{A}_u = \mathcal{S}_u$ and $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ is weakly compatible, $\mathcal{A}_w = \mathcal{A}\mathcal{S}_u = \mathcal{S}\mathcal{A}_u = \mathcal{S}_w$. Now, we demonstrate that w is a shared fixed point between \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{S} . Putting $a = w$ and $b = v$ in (1), we have

$$\Omega(\mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_w - \mathfrak{B}_v, p\sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{S}_w - \mathcal{T}_v, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_w - \mathcal{S}_w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathfrak{B}_v - \mathcal{T}_v, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_w - \mathcal{T}_v, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathfrak{B}_v - \mathcal{S}_w, \sigma)) \geq 0$$

and so

$$\Omega(\mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_w - w, p\sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_w - \mathcal{A}_w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w - \mathcal{A}_w, \sigma)) \geq 0$$

Or equivalently,

$$\Omega(\mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_w - w, p\sigma), \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_w - w, \sigma), 1, 1, \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{H}(w - \mathcal{A}_w, \sigma)) \geq 0$$

we obtain $\mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_w - w, p\sigma) \geq \mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}_w - w, \sigma)$ from Ω_1 and Ω_2 . $\mathcal{A}_w = w = \mathcal{S}_w$, which demonstrates that w is a common fixed point of $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$,

Furthermore, $\mathfrak{B}_v = \mathcal{T}_v$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{S})$ is weakly compatible, then $\mathfrak{B}_w = \mathfrak{B}\mathcal{T}_v = \mathcal{T}\mathfrak{B}_v = \mathcal{T}_w$. On using (1) with $a = u, b = w$. we have $\Omega(\mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_u - \mathfrak{B}_w, p\sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{S}_u - \mathcal{T}_w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_u - \mathcal{S}_u, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_w - \mathcal{T}_w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_u - \mathcal{T}_w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_w - \mathcal{S}_u, \sigma)) \geq 0$

which reduces to

$$\Omega(\mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_w, p\sigma), \mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_w, \sigma), 1, 1, \mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_w - w, \sigma)) \geq 0$$

And so

$$\Omega(\mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_w, p\sigma), \mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_w - \mathcal{B}_w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_w - w, \sigma)) \geq 0,$$

We obtain $\mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_w, p\sigma) \geq \mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_w, \sigma)$ from Ω_1 and Ω_2 . w is fixed point that both \mathfrak{B} and \mathcal{T} share. As a result, w is fixed point shared by mapping $\mathcal{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathcal{S}$ and \mathcal{T} . Given Ω_1 and Ω_2 , the inequality (1) naturally leads to the uniqueness of the shared fixed point.

Example 3.1:

For instance, assume that $(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{S}, *)$ if fuzzy normed space with $\mathcal{U} = [1, 15)$, normed find $x * y = \min\{x, y\}$ for all $x, y \in [0, 1]$ and $\mathfrak{S}(a, \sigma) = \begin{cases} \frac{\sigma}{\sigma + \|a\|} & , \sigma > 0 \\ 0 & , \sigma = 0 \end{cases}$ for all $\sigma > 0$ and $a \in \mathcal{U}$. The self-mapping $\mathcal{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathcal{S}$ and \mathcal{T} are defined as follows.

$$\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{U}) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } a \in \{1\} \cup (3, 5); \\ 14, & \text{if } a \in (1, 3], \end{cases}$$

$$\mathfrak{B}(\mathcal{U}) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } a \in \{1\} \cup (3, 15); \\ 5, & \text{if } a \in (1, 3], \end{cases}$$

$$\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U}) = \begin{cases} 1 & , a = 1 \\ \frac{7}{2} & , a \in (1, 3] \\ \frac{a+1}{4} & , a \in (3, 15) \end{cases}, \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U}) = \begin{cases} 1 & , a = 1 \\ 9 + a & , a \in (1, 3] \\ a - 2 & , a \in (3, 15) \end{cases}$$

$\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U})$ and $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$ are not closed subset of \mathcal{U} , as demonstrated by the fact that $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{U}) = \{1, 14\} \not\subseteq [1, 13) = \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$, $\mathfrak{B}(\mathcal{U}) = \{1, 15\} \not\subseteq [1, 4) = \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U})$. Examine $\Omega: [0, 1]^6 \rightarrow R$ as it is described in example (2.2) it is evident that if we select two sequences, $\{a_n\} = \{3 + \frac{1}{n}\}$, $\{b_n\} = \{1\}$ (Or $\{a_n\} = \{1\}$, $\{b_n\} = \{3 + \frac{1}{n}\}$) then $n \rightarrow \infty$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{A}_{a_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{S}_{a_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{b_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{T}_{b_n} = 1 \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U}) \cap \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$. Therefore, the $(CLR_{\mathcal{S}\mathcal{T}})$ property is satisfied by both pair $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{S})$. The inequality can be confirmed by a simple computation (1). Therefore, for some given $p \in (0, 1)$, every criterion of Theorem 3.1 are met, and 1 is a single common fixed point of the pairings $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{S})$ and $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$, which additionally continues to be a point of coincidence. Furthermore, at their distinct common fixed point 1, all the related mappings are even discontinuous.

Theorem 3.2: Let $(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{S}, *)$ be a *fns* such that for every $\sigma \in [0, 1]$, $\sigma * \sigma \geq \sigma$. Let \mathcal{U} be mapped onto itself by $\mathcal{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathcal{S}$ and \mathcal{T} . Assume the following hypothesis and the inequality (1) are true: $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U})$ and $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$ are closed subsets of \mathcal{U} , and $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{S})$ satisfy the common property $(E.A)$. Following, that, each of the pair $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{S})$ has a coincidence point. Furthermore, if both $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{S})$ are weakly compatible, then there is a single fixed point shared by $\mathcal{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathcal{S}$ and \mathcal{T} .

Proof: There are two sequences $\{a_n\}$ and $\{b_n\}$ in \mathcal{U} and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{A}_{a_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{S}_{a_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{b_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{T}_{b_n} = w$, for some $w \in \mathcal{U}$, given that the pairings $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{S})$ share the common property $(E.A)$. $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{S}_{a_n} = w \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U})$ since $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U})$ is closed subset of \mathcal{U} . As a result, there is a point $u \in \mathcal{U}$ where $\mathcal{S}_u = w$. Also, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{T}_{a_n} = w \in \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$ indicating that $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$ is a closed subset of \mathcal{U} . Consequently, there is a point v in \mathcal{U} where $\mathcal{T}_v = w$. The remainder of the proof follows the same path as the proof of the Theorem 3.1.

Example 3.2: Change out the mappings $\mathcal{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathcal{S}$ and \mathcal{T} in Example 3.1 with the following while keeping the others the same:

$$\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{U}) = \begin{cases} 1 & , \quad \text{if } a \in \{1\} \cup (3, 5); \\ 14 & , \quad \text{if } a \in (1, 3], \end{cases}$$

$$\mathfrak{B}(X) = \begin{cases} 1 & , \quad \text{if } a \in \{1\} \cup (3, 15); \\ 5 & , \quad \text{if } a \in (1, 3], \end{cases}$$

$$\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U}) = \begin{cases} 1 & , a = 1 \\ 4 & , a \in (1, 3] \\ \frac{a+1}{4} & , a \in (3, 15) \end{cases}, \quad \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U}) = \begin{cases} 1 & , a = 1 \\ 10 + x & , a \in (1, 3] \\ a - 2 & , a \in (3, 15) \end{cases}$$

Consequently, $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U})$ and $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$ are closed subsets of \mathcal{U} since $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{U}) = \{1, 14\} \not\subset [1, 13] = \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$ and $\mathfrak{B}(\mathcal{U}) = \{1, 5\} \not\subset [1, 4] = \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U})$. Examining two sequences as shown in Example 3.1, it is evident that the pairs $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{T})$ share the characteristic (E.A), which is $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{A}_{a_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{S}_{a_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{b_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{T}_{b_n} = 1 \in \mathcal{U}$. Thus, for some given $p \in (0, 1)$, all the criteria of Theorem 3.2 are satisfied, and 1 is a unique shared fixed pint of the pairings $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{T})$, which also continues to be a point of coincidence.

Theorem 3.3: Let $(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{N}, *)$ be a *fns* such that for every $\sigma \in [0, 1], \sigma * \sigma \geq \sigma$. Let \mathcal{U} be mapped onto itself by $\mathcal{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathcal{S}$ and \mathcal{T} , meeting every hypothesis in Lemma 3.1. After then, each of the pairs $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{T})$ has a coincidence point. Furthermore, if both pairs and $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{T})$ are weakly compatible, then $\mathcal{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathcal{S}$ and \mathcal{T} share a single fixed point.

Proof: The pairs $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{T})$ satisfy the $(CLR_{\mathcal{S}\mathcal{T}})$ property in light of Lemma 3.1. Two sequences $\{a_n\}$ and $\{b_n\}$ in \mathcal{U} such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{A}_{a_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{S}_{a_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{b_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{T}_{b_n} = w$, for some $w \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U}) \cap \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$. The remainder of the proof can be finished along the lines of the Theorem 3.1.

Example 3.3: Replace the self-mappings $\mathcal{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathcal{S}$ and \mathcal{T} in Example 3.1, with the following while keeping the others same:

$$\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{U}) = \begin{cases} 1 & , \quad \text{if } a \in \{1\} \cup (3, 15); \\ 5 & , \quad \text{if } a \in (1, 3], \end{cases}$$

$$\mathfrak{B}(\mathcal{U}) = \begin{cases} 1 & , \quad \text{if } a \in \{1\} \cup (3, 15); \\ 4 & , \quad \text{if } a \in (1, 3], \end{cases}$$

$$\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U}) = \begin{cases} 1 & , a = 1 \\ 4 & , a \in (1, 3] \\ \frac{a+1}{4} & , a \in (3, 15) \end{cases}$$

$$\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U}) = \begin{cases} 1 & , a = 1 \\ 10 + a & , a \in (1, 3] \\ a - 2 & , a \in (3, 15) \end{cases}$$

In order to demonstrate that $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U})$ and $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$ are closed subsets of \mathcal{U} , we derive $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{U}) = \{1, 5\} \subset [1, 13] = \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{U})$ and $\mathfrak{B}(\mathcal{U}) = \{1, 4\} \subset [1, 4] = \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{U})$. With a simple computation, one can confirm the inequality 3.1 for all $a, b \in \mathcal{U}$ and for some fixed $p \in (0, 1)$. Consequently, Theorem 3.3 's requirements are all met, and 1 is a single common fixed point of the pairings $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{T})$ and $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$, this continues to be a point of coincidence.

Corollary 3.1: Let $(\mathcal{U}, \mathfrak{N}, *)$ be a fuzzy normed space such that for every $\sigma \in [0, 1], \sigma * \sigma \geq \sigma$. Let \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S} be mapping from \mathcal{U} into itself that meet the requirements listed below:

1. \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S} satisfies the $(CLR_{\mathcal{S}\mathcal{T}})$ condition.
2. $\exists p \in (0, 1)$ and

$\Omega(\mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_a - \mathfrak{B}_b, p\sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{S}_a - \mathcal{S}_b, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_a - \mathcal{S}_a, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_b - \mathcal{S}_b, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_a - \mathcal{S}_b, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_b - \mathcal{S}_a, \sigma)) \geq 0$,
 $\forall a, b \in \mathfrak{U}, \sigma > 0, \Omega \in \Omega_6$. then there is a point of coincidence between \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{S} . Furthermore, \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{S} share a single fixed point if they are a weakly compatible pair.

APPLICATIONS

In this part, we present and established an integral version of theorem(3.1) to achieve this, we first must demonstrate the subsequent lemma within the framework of fuzzy normed spaces.

Lemma 4.1: Let $(\mathfrak{U}, \mathfrak{S}, *)$ be a *fns* such that for every $\sigma \in [0, 1], \sigma * \sigma \geq \sigma$. If there exists a constant $p \in (0, 1)$ such that for any $a \in \mathfrak{U}, \sigma > 0$,

$$\int_0^{\mathfrak{S}(a, p\sigma)} \wp(s) ds \geq \int_0^{\mathfrak{S}(a, \sigma)} \wp(s) ds \quad (2)$$

where $\wp: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a non-negative summable integrable function of Lebesgue and $\int_{\varepsilon}^1 \wp(s) ds > 0$, for each $\varepsilon \in [0, 1)$, then $a = 0$.

Proof: we may inductively write for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\int_0^{\mathfrak{S}(a, p^n \sigma)} \wp(s) ds \geq \int_0^{\mathfrak{S}(a, \sigma)} \wp(s) ds$

$$\int_0^{\mathfrak{S}(a, \sigma)} \wp(s) ds \geq \int_0^{\mathfrak{S}(a, p^{-1}\sigma)} \wp(s) ds \geq \int_0^{\mathfrak{S}(a, p^{-2}\sigma)} \wp(s) ds \geq \dots \geq \int_0^{\mathfrak{S}(a, p^{-n}\sigma)} \wp(s) ds \rightarrow \int_0^1 \wp(s) ds,$$

which implies $\int_0^{\mathfrak{S}(a, \sigma)} \wp(s) ds - \int_0^1 \wp(s) ds \geq 0$, as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

And so $\int_0^{\mathfrak{S}(a, \sigma)} \wp(s) ds - (\int_0^{\mathfrak{S}(a, \sigma)} \wp(s) ds + \int_{\mathfrak{S}(a, \sigma)}^1 \wp(s) ds) \geq 0$, or equivalently,

$$\int_{\mathfrak{S}(a, \sigma)}^1 \wp(s) ds \leq 0 \text{ implying } \mathfrak{S}(a, \sigma) = 1 \forall, \sigma \geq 0. \text{ We then have } a = 0.$$

Theorem 4.1: Let $(\mathfrak{U}, \mathfrak{S}, *)$ be a *fns* such that for every $\sigma \in [0, 1], \sigma * \sigma \geq \sigma$. Let \mathfrak{U} be mapped onto itself by $\mathcal{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathcal{S}$ and \mathcal{T} . Assume that a function $\Omega \in \Omega_6$ exists that satisfies

$$\int_0^{\Omega(u, v, v, v, v)} \wp(s) ds \geq 0 \quad (3)$$

where $\wp: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a non-negative summable integrable function of Lebesgue and for every $\varepsilon \in [0, 1), \int_{\varepsilon}^1 \wp(s) ds > 0, u \geq v \forall u, v \in [0, 1]$. Assume that the $(CLR_{\mathcal{ST}})$ property is shared by the pairings $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{S})$. There exist $p \in (0, 1), p$ constant, such that

$$\int_0^{\Omega(\mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_a - \mathfrak{B}_b, p\sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{S}_a - \mathcal{T}_b, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_a - \mathcal{S}_a, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_b - \mathcal{T}_b, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_a - \mathcal{T}_b, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_b - \mathcal{S}_a, \sigma))} \wp(s) ds \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

$\forall a \in \mathfrak{U}, \sigma > 0$, then there is a point of coincidence between the pairings $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{S})$.

Furthermore, $\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{S}, \mathcal{A}$, and \mathcal{S} share a single common fixed point if both pairs $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{S})$ and $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ are weakly compatible.

Proof: Given that the $(CLR_{\mathcal{ST}})$ condition is shared by the pairings $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ and $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathcal{T})$, \mathfrak{U} contain the sequences $\{a_n\}$ and $\{b_n\}$ in \mathfrak{U} such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{A}_{a_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{S}_{a_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{b_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{T}_{b_n} = w$, where w is a member of $\mathcal{S}(\mathfrak{U}) \cap \mathcal{T}(\mathfrak{U})$. There is a point $u \in \mathfrak{U}$ such that $\mathcal{S}_u = w$ since $w \in \mathcal{S}(\mathfrak{U})$. We now claim that $\mathcal{A}_u = \mathcal{S}_u$ when $a = u, b = b_n$, used with (4), have

$\int_0^{\infty} \mathfrak{Q}(\mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_u - \mathfrak{B}_{b_n}, p\sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{S}_u - \mathcal{T}_{b_n}, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_u - \mathcal{S}_u, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_{b_n} - \mathcal{T}_{b_n}, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_u - \mathcal{T}_{b_n}, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_{b_n} - \mathcal{S}_u, \sigma)) \wp(s) ds \geq 0$. Considering $n \rightarrow \infty$ as the limit, we obtain

$$0 \leq \int_0^{\infty} \mathfrak{Q}(\mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_u - w, p\sigma), \mathfrak{S}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_u - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(u - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(w - w, \sigma)) \wp(s) ds, \text{ and therefore}$$

$$0 \leq \int_0^{\infty} \mathfrak{Q}(\mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_u - w, p\sigma), 1, \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_u - w, \sigma), 1, \mathfrak{S}(u - w, \sigma), 1) \wp(s) ds, \text{ since } \mathfrak{Q} \text{ is decreasing in } \sigma.$$

We obtain $\mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_u - w, p\sigma) \geq \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_u - w, \sigma)$ from (3). Using Lemma (3.1), we can see that u is a coincidence point of the pair $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{S})$ since $\mathcal{A}_u - w$ and hence $\mathcal{A}_u = \mathcal{S}_u - w$. There is $v \in \mathfrak{U}$ and $\mathcal{T}_v = w$ since $w \in \mathcal{T}(\mathfrak{U})$ as well. We now demonstrate that $\mathfrak{B}_v = \mathcal{T}_v$. When $a - u = 0$ and $b - v = 0$, we obtain

$$\int_0^{\infty} \mathfrak{Q}(\mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_u - \mathfrak{B}_v, p\sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{S}_u - \mathcal{T}_v, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_u - \mathcal{S}_u, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_v - \mathcal{T}_v, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathcal{A}_u - \mathcal{T}_v, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_v - \mathcal{S}_u, \sigma)) \wp(s) ds \geq 0,$$

Or conversely,

$$\int_0^{\infty} \mathfrak{Q}(\mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_v, p\sigma), \mathfrak{S}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_v - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(w - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_v - w, \sigma)) \wp(s) ds \geq 0$$

and so

$$\int_0^{\infty} \mathfrak{Q}(\mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_v, p\sigma), 1, 1, \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_v - w, \sigma), 1, \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_v - w, \sigma)) \wp(s) ds \geq 0,$$

Since \mathfrak{Q} is decreasing in $\sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, \sigma_5, \sigma_6$. We obtain

$$\int_0^{\infty} \mathfrak{Q}(\mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_v, p\sigma), \mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_v, p\sigma), \mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_v, p\sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_v - w, \sigma), \mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_v, p\sigma), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{B}_v - w, \sigma)) \wp(s) ds \geq 0,$$

We obtain $\mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_v, p\sigma) \geq \mathfrak{S}(w - \mathfrak{B}_v, \sigma)$ from (4.2). $\mathfrak{B}_v = w = \mathcal{T}_w$, which indicates that w is a shared fixed point of $(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{S})$, is obtained by invoking Lemma (3.1). As a result, w is a fixed point shared by $\mathcal{A}, \mathfrak{B}, \mathcal{S}$ and \mathcal{T} . An obvious outcome of the inequality (4.3) is the uniqueness of the common fixed point.

CONCLUSION

This study focuses on leveraging the common limit characteristic (CLR) to establish generalized fixed point results for weakly compatible functions in fuzzy normed spaces (fns) under an implicit condition. Through carefully constructed examples, we demonstrate the validity of our assumptions and the practical significance of our results. Moreover, as an application of our primary findings, we present an integral-based fixed point theorem in fns, further expanding the scope of fixed point studies in fuzzy environments.

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